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MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

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**ASSESSMENT OF AGUSAN MARSH WILDLIFE SANCTUARY (AMWS)
PEATLAND'S RESILIENCE TO CLIMATE CHANGE, SOCIO-ECONOMIC, AND
ENVIRONMENTAL STRESSORS BY ESTIMATING SOIL SURFACE MOISTURE
USING REMOTE SENSING**

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05 May 2024

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ASSESSMENT OF AGUSAN MARSH WILDLIFE SANCTUARY (AMWS) PEATLAND'S RESILIENCE TO CLIMATE CHANGE, SOCIO-ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL STRESSORS BY ESTIMATING SOIL SURFACE MOISTURE USING REMOTE SENSING

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This Special Problem titled: **“ASSESSMENT OF AGUSAN MARSH WILDLIFE SANCTUARY (AMWS) PEATLAND’S RESILIENCE TO CLIMATE CHANGE, SOCIO-ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL STRESSORS BY ESTIMATING SOIL SURFACE MOISTURE USING REMOTE SENSING”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

SHAIRA E. BALIDOY

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Abstract

This study focuses on assessing the resilience of peatlands within the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) to climate change, socio-economic activities, and environmental stressors, with a specific emphasis on soil moisture dynamics. Using remote sensing techniques, the study evaluates changes in soil surface moisture following the sanctuary's boundary expansion in 2018. Additionally, it identifies and analyzes the top stressors affecting peatland resilience, considering factors such as climate change, socio-economic activities, and environmental degradation. The results reveal an increase in moisture levels within the Marbon Peatland area and fluctuations in moisture distribution within the Caimpugan Peatland area. The study highlights soil moisture as the primary indicator of peatland resilience, supported by factors such as temperature anomalies and illegal activities such as cutting of trees and timber poaching, and land conversion. Moreover, it underscores the significant impact of socio-economic stressors on AMWS, comprising 34% of total threats, while climate change and environmental stressors also contribute substantially 23% and 27%, respectively. The findings suggest that addressing these stressors is essential for enhancing the resilience of peatlands in AMWS. Overall, this study provides valuable insights for the development of conservation and management strategies to safeguard the peatland ecosystem within the sanctuary.

Keywords: Remote Sensing; Peatland; Soil Moisture; Climate Change; Sanctuary

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the critical biodiversity hotspots in the Philippines is the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS), which has a wide variety of flora and fauna within its unique peatland ecosystem. Like any other conservational ecosystem, AMWS is also suffering from low to high threats coming from climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors. AMWS has two peatland deposits, and understanding its resilience to climate change and environmental stressors is essential in conservation and sustainable management.

AMWS was proclaimed a protected area under Republic Act (RA) No. 7586, otherwise known as the National Integrated Protected Areas System (NIPAS) Act, by Presidential Proclamation 913 dated October 31, 1996, with a total area of 19,196 ha (DENR-PENRO, 2022). The RAMSAR Convention included it in the Wetlands of International Importance list on November 12, 1999, for it is one of Asia's crucial transit points for wild birds. In 2002, a bill was lobbied for enacting an Act to expand the total area to 40,940 ha from 19,196 ha as proposed in Senate Bills No. 176 and 1071 during the 14th Congress (see Figure 1).

The expansion was approved and included in RA No. 11038: Expanded National Integrated Protected Areas System Act, or the E-NIPAS Act of 2018. The expansion includes two peatlands, the Caimpugan Peatland and Marbon, Talacogon Peatland, the major reason for the expansion aside from the Crocodile Sanctuary (Figure 2).

The study aims to assess the resilience of the AMWS peatlands, the Caimpugan and Marbon, Talacogon peatlands ecosystem through remote sensing technology by estimating soil surface moisture levels. Soil surface moisture is one factor in analyzing

the ecosystem's health, vegetation diversity, hydrological condition, and overall Assessment of Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) Peatland's Resilience 1 to Climate Change, Socio-Economic, and Environmental Stressors by Estimating Soil Surface Moisture Using Remote Sensing

ecosystem functions (Barnard et al., 2009). Determining the soil moisture levels using remote sensing can provide insights into the vulnerability of AMWS peatlands to climate-induced changes and its capability to withstand or recover from other environmental threats (Scanlon et al., 2005).

Figure 1. The map on the right shows the old boundary (in red) and the expanded boundary (in black). The map on the left side highlights the two peatlands in color blue and pink. Maps source from AMWS-PAMO, DENR, 2015.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In the study "Mapping Land Cover Change and Modelling its Impacts on the Inundation Responses of the Agusan Marsh, Mindanao, Philippines," Makinano-Santillan and Santillan (2021), analyzed the land cover change in the Agusan Marsh, a vital wetland ecosystem in Mindanao. Through remote sensing techniques and modeling approaches, they assessed the impacts of land cover change on the inundation responses of the marsh.

Based on the insights from Makinano-Santillan and Santillan's study, this paper aims to expand our understanding of the correlations between land cover change, soil moisture dynamics, and ecosystem resilience in the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary. Through the use of remote sensing techniques and modeling approaches, this research seeks to quantitatively analyze the impacts of land cover change on soil surface moisture levels and assess their implications for the resilience of the peatland ecosystem. This approach can provide valuable inputs for guiding conservation and management efforts to enhance the AMWS peatland's resilience to ongoing environmental changes.

The Agusan River Basin has a Type 2 climate based on the Corona classification. Type 2 is characterized by the absence of a dry season and very pronounced maximum rainfall from November to January (DENR-NWRB, 2008). Although there are no historical records of drought in the AMWS, the study assessed the soil moisture levels to determine whether the peatlands are affected by environmental and climatic changes.

Satellite remote sensing has become an invaluable tool for estimating soil moisture levels in regions like the Gumara Catchment, Ethiopia, where ground-based

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measurements may be limited. Studies by Gebrehiwot et al. (2019) and Hülsmann et al. (2018) have demonstrated the effectiveness of utilizing data from satellite missions such as Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 to derive soil moisture estimates, leveraging optical and microwave sensors for comprehensive coverage and accurate predictions. Additionally, research by Liu et al. (2020) highlights the potential of machine learning algorithms, particularly artificial neural networks, for mapping soil moisture content using multi-temporal satellite imagery and ground-based measurements, offering improved spatial and temporal resolution. Integrating these remote sensing techniques and advanced modeling approaches is promising for enhancing soil moisture estimation in data-scarce regions like the Gumara Catchment, facilitating informed decision-making for sustainable land management practices.

In addition to climate change impacts, this research also considers other threats from socio-economic and environmental drivers influencing the resilience of the AMWS peatland. By integrating socio-economic data and environmental indicators, we can evaluate the interactions between human activities, land-use changes, and ecosystem dynamics within the AMWS (Lambin et al., 2001).

AHP is a widely recognized approach to address complex decision-making problems. It implements a systematic framework that involves pairwise comparisons. The process is structured hierarchically, with significant components set out in order. AHP utilizes criteria pairs and expert interviews to assess for pairwise comparison that determines the alternatives and priorities. In order to prevent from deciding incorrect alternatives and criteria, decision-makers and/or experts respond to questions/inquiries while examining the accessible data at hand.

AHP can be utilized in various decision-making situations, making it adaptable, flexible, and a stand-alone tool. This study emphasizes AHP's contribution to decision-making and the development of confidence and expertise. AHP's broader implications are in the context of sustainable development, in examining and selecting complex economic and other systems from diverse perspectives (Fountzoula, 2021).

In implementing AHP, key informant interviews (KII) are vital. They strengthen decision-making by providing insights and perspectives. These interviews not only amplify comprehension regarding decision structures but also secure expert insights and information for possibilities, alternatives, and criteria (Saaty, 2004).

KII promotes collaboration and participation, which increases the validity and acceptance of results. The experts' knowledge and expertise help mitigate potential biases because they reflect a commitment to transparent, inclusive decisions. This interdisciplinary approach will provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping the resilience of the AMWS peatland and inform evidence-based strategies for its conservation and management.

Overall, this special problem seeks to contribute to the conservation and sustainable management of the AMWS peatland ecosystem by assessing its resilience to climate change, socio-economic pressures, and environmental stressors. By harnessing the power of remote sensing technology and interdisciplinary research methodologies, this study aims to generate valuable insights into the adaptive capacity of the AMWS peatland and support informed decision-making for its preservation and protection.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The primary problem of this study is assessing the resilience of AMWS peatlands to climate change, socio-economic activities, and environmental stressors, focusing on soil moisture dynamics. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Evaluate the present soil surface moisture condition in the peatlands of AMWS using remote sensing techniques and correlate it with the impact of the boundary expansion in 2018, alongside temperature anomalies and rainfall rates.
2. Identify the top stressors from climate change, socio-economic, and environmental to the peatland resilience; and
3. Formulate strategies for enhancing the resilience of AMWS's peatland to withstand the stressors coming from climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors.

This special problem aims to provide valuable insights into the factors affecting AMWS peatlands' resilience and contribute to developing effective conservation and management strategies for the wetland sanctuary.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objectives of this special problem were to evaluate peatland resilience, analyze effects on peatland natural resources, and recommend strategies and activities to help the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary withstand peatland degradation.

The specific objectives were to: (1) evaluate peatland resilience through soil moisture analysis, (2) conduct time-bound comparative analysis before and after the expansion, (3) correlate soil moisture to climatic changes of temperature and rainfall rate using remote sensing, (4) identify the top stressors from climate change, environmental, and socio-economic stressors, and (5) recommend strategies to help the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary withstand the peatland degradation due to climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors.

By addressing these objectives, the study aimed to contribute to the scientific understanding of peatland resilience and inform proactive measures for the conservation and sustainable management of the AMWS and similar ecosystems.

V. RATIONALE

The Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) is a critical biodiversity hotspot, providing habitat for diverse flora and fauna (Hoeinghaus et al., 2007). Understanding the resilience of the peatland ecosystem within AMWS to climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors is crucial for devising effective conservation strategies to protect this unique ecosystem and its inhabitants.

Human activities, including land-use changes and socio-economic development, can exert considerable pressure on the AMWS peatland ecosystem (Lambin et al., 2001). Integrating socio-economic data into the assessment allows for an understanding of the interactions between human activities, land-use changes, and ecosystem dynamics. This holistic approach is essential for addressing the socio-economic drivers of environmental degradation and promoting sustainable resource management practices.

Remote sensing technology for estimating soil surface moisture offers a noninvasive and cost-effective approach to monitoring environmental changes over large spatial scales and long time periods (Pettorelli et al., 2014). By leveraging remote sensing data, the study can provide timely and accurate information on soil moisture dynamics within the AMWS peatland, enabling informed decision-making for ecosystem management and conservation.

The study findings can have significant policy and management implications for the AMWS and similar peatland ecosystems globally. By identifying areas of high resilience and vulnerability within the AMWS peatland, policymakers, and resource managers can prioritize conservation efforts, allocate resources effectively, and

implement adaptive management strategies to enhance the ecosystem's resilience in the face of ongoing environmental changes.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The following are the aspects with specific scope and limitations for this special problem:

1. **Study Area.** This special problem focused on the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) located in Agusan del Sur, Philippines, particularly on the two (2) peatlands, the Caimpugan and Marbon, Talacogon.
2. **Soil Moisture Analysis.** The analysis is limited to soil moisture analysis as a proxy for peatland resilience using Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data ArcMap 10.4. Images downloaded from EarthExplorer United State of Geological Survey (USGS) through Landsat 8-9 Operational Land Imager (OLI) / Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) Landsat Collection-2 (C2) in Level 2 (L2) satellite.
3. **Stressors.** The threat indicators were identified from the AMWS Management Plan 2014-2019. Ten key informants from Academe, Environmental Management Bureau, National Irrigation Administration, Department of Environment and Natural Resources-Community Environment and Natural Resources, private company, and Local Government Unit answered the pair-wise questionnaire.
4. **Validation Method.** Fieldwork logistics, including access to certain areas within AMWS and weather conditions, may limit the scope of data collection. For the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach, the researcher calculated the consistency ratio of each key informant to conclude that the response and questionnaire were consistent.

5. **Result and Findings.** The recommendation based on findings may be influenced by uncertainties inherent in remote sensing and data processing.
6. **Time and Resource Constraints.** Time and resource constraints can reduce the depth of analysis and limit the comprehensiveness of findings.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE AREA

Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary is located in Northeastern Mindanao, in the Province of Agusan del Sur, covering some parts of the six (6) municipalities of Talacogon, San Francisco, Lapaz, Rosario, Bunawan, and Loreto with a total of thirty-three (33) barangays. The map in Figure 2 shows the boundaries of AMWS, indicating its strict protection and buffer zone boundaries (Campos, n.d.) and the overall AMWS boundary under the ENIPAS Act (RA No. 11038). The map also shows the existing facilities within and nearby AMWS, including households, municipalities and barangay boundaries, and other facilities relevant to the management of AMWS.

Figure 2. Location of the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary and the existing facilities. Map source from AMWS-PAMO, DENR, 2015.

AMWS is the largest and least disturbed freshwater wetland in the country. The marsh plays an important ecological role in the CARAGA Region, being the catch basin of the Davao-Agusan plains.

AMWS was proclaimed a protected area under RA 7586, or the National Integrated Protected Areas System (NIPAS) Act, by Presidential Proclamation 913 dated October 31, 1996, with a total area of 19,196 ha. A House Bill was lobbied and approved on June 22, 2018, to enact the expansion of the total area to 40,940 ha, based on the proposed Senate Bill No. 176 and 1071.

AMWS was included in the Wetlands of International Importance list by the RAMSAR Convention on November 12, 1999, for it is one of Asia's crucial transit points for wild birds. Many migratory birds spend less than a year in the marsh to breed or avoid the cold wind brought by the winter season of Northern Asia (DENR-PENRO, 2022).

Strict protection zones pertain to the management zones of protected areas consisting of natural areas with high biodiversity values. They are closed to all human activities except for scientific studies and/or ceremonial or religious use by the ICCs/IPs. It may include habitats of threatened species or degraded areas designated for reforestation and subsequent protection, even if these areas are still in various stages of regeneration (PAMB-AMWS, 2015). Meanwhile, the buffer zones are identified outside the boundaries immediately adjacent to designated protected areas according to section 8 of the NIPAS Act that need special development control to avoid or minimize harm to the protected area (PAMB-AMWS, 2015).

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The study made use of the following methods: (1) Remote Sensing for soil moisture analysis and correlations of rainfall and temperature climatic changes, and (2) Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to identify the top stressor in AMWS coming from climatic changes, environmental, and socio-economic threats.

Soil Moisture Analysis through Remote Sensing using ArcGIS

The first method used in this special problem was to evaluate peatland resilience by utilizing Sentinel-1 SAR data in remote sensing to estimate soil surface moisture and assess the resilience of the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) peatland ecosystem to climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors (Fernández-Manso et al., 2018).

Next, a time-bound comparative analysis of soil surface moisture levels before and after the boundary expansion of AMWS in 2018 was conducted to determine the expansion's impact on peatland resilience (Leblanc et al., 2019).

The third step was to correlate the soil moisture analysis results to temperature changes and rainfall rate to investigate the potential effects of boundary expansion on natural resources, particularly the peatland ecosystem, through a comprehensive analysis of soil surface moisture dynamics (Wang et al., 2018).

Soil moisture analysis utilized remote sensing using ArcMap 10.4 through the raster calculation of Normalized Difference Index Moisture (NDMI), Near Infrared Reflectivity (NIR), and Short Waved Infrared Reflectivity (SWIR). ArcGIS and ArcMap were among the software tools and server software used to view, edit, manage, and

analyze geographical data (GISGeography, 2021). The process flow summarized the methodologies used in this study.

Landsat Images were obtained from Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS C2 L2 data covering the AMWS peatland area. Socio-economic data and environmental indicators relevant to the study area were collected. Pre-processing of Sentinel-1 SAR data was done to remove noise and artifacts, ensuring data quality for subsequent analysis. This included calibration, filtering, and geometric correction of the satellite imagery. Supervised classification of the pre-processed Sentinel-1 SAR data using software tools such as ArcGIS or QGIS was then conducted. A classification algorithm was implemented to differentiate soil surface moisture levels within the peatland area. The classified Sentinel-1 SAR data was analyzed to estimate soil surface moisture levels across the AMWS peatlands. Remote sensing techniques were utilized to map and visualize spatial variations in soil moisture within the study area.

Figure 3. Process flow of the special problem's methodology.

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

This special problem applied the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) to recommend strategies and activities to help the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary withstand peatland degradation due to climate change, socio-economic, and environmental stressors.

Table 1 presents the scale for assessing the intensity of importance between two indicators in vulnerability components. It ranged from 1 to 9, where 1 indicated equal importance, 3 denoted moderate importance favoring Indicator A slightly over Indicator B, 5 represented strong importance favoring Indicator A, 7 indicated very strong importance favoring Indicator A, and 9 signified extreme importance of Indicator A over Indicator B. Intermediate values 2, 4, 6, and 8 were used when compromise was necessary, while reciprocals like $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{4}$, and $\frac{1}{3}$ were employed for elements closely matched in importance.

Table 1

Rating Scale for The Pairwise Comparison of Indicators from AMWS

INTENSITY OF IMPORTANCE	DESCRIPTION	EXPLANATION
1	Equal Importance	The two indicators have equal contribution to the vulnerability component
3	Moderate Importance	Importance contribution of Indicator A is slightly favored over Indicator B
5	Strong Importance	Contribution of Indicator A is strongly favored over Indicator B
7	Very Strong Importance	Contribution of Indicator A is strongly favored over Indicator B

INTENSITY OF IMPORTANCE	DESCRIPTION	EXPLANATION
9	Extreme Importance	Indicator A has the highest possible contribution over Indicator B
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate Values	When compromise is needed
Reciprocals: ½, ¼, 1/3, etc.	These intensities can be used for elements that are very close in importance	

Note: Adapted from T.L. Saaty, 2004, pp. 1-35.

The three primary stressors affecting the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS)—climate change, environmental threats, and socio-economic factors—were reflected in Table 2. Climate change stressors included shifts in rainfall patterns and temperature anomalies, impacting peatland health and carbon sequestration. Environmental threats encompassed illegal cutting of trees or timber poaching, mining activities, and poor waste management, leading to habitat degradation and water pollution. Socio-economic factors such as illegal settlements, unsustainable livelihoods, and inadequate governance exacerbated these challenges, highlighting the need for comprehensive conservation strategies and collaborative action to safeguard AMWS biodiversity and ecological integrity.

Table 2

Identified Stressors from Climate-change, Environmental, and Socio-economic

Stressors Type	No.	Specific Stressors	Remarks
Climate Change	1	Change in Rainfall Rate	While moderate increases in rainfall may benefit peatlands, there exists a tipping point beyond which excessive precipitation can trigger irreversible damage, such as increased erosion, reduced carbon storage,

Stressors Type	No.	Specific Stressors	Remarks
			and loss of biodiversity (Gallego-Sala et al. (2018).
	2	Temperature Anomalies	Elevated temperatures can accelerate the decomposition of organic matter within peat, leading to increased carbon dioxide emissions and loss of carbon sequestration capacity.
Environmental	3	Illegal cutting of Trees	Despite AMWS being declared a Protected Area, some areas face ongoing threats such as timber poaching and conversion to agriculture, altering the ecological balance and wildlife habitats (PASAKK, 2014).
	4	Small-scale mining upland	Livelihoods in municipalities around AMWS include fishing and small-scale mining, with mining posing the greatest ecological threat due to mine tailings contaminating water bodies (PASAKK, 2014).
	5	Sedimentation nutrient loading	Land use conversion to agriculture increases soil erosion and pollution from agrochemicals, impacting water quality, with mining operations being a major source of pollution (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
	6	Poor solid waste management	Efforts to manage solid waste in the area face challenges like lack of segregation and waste burning, leading to pollution of water bodies and AMWS (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
	7	Eutrophication	Direct disposal of domestic sewage into water bodies causes eutrophication, reducing oxygen levels and harming aquatic life (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
Socio-economic	8	Illegal settlement	Subsistence farmers and fisherfolk resort to illegal activities like timber poaching due to limited livelihood options (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
	9	Unsustainable livelihood	Tourism potential in AMWS was highlighted during the captivity of crocodile Lolong but declined afterward due to lack of sustained development (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
	10	Conversion of land to agriculture	Despite tourism opportunities, there's a lack of coordinated effort by the government and private sectors to develop AMWS as a tourist destination (Pasicolan et al., 2014).
	11	Weak tourism	Land speculation and squatting, disguised under IPRA Law, threaten AMWS integrity

Stressors Type	No.	Specific Stressors	Remarks
			and serve political interests (KII and FGD, July 2014).
	12	Lack of IP representation in PAMB	Low IP community representation in PAMB makes it challenging to implement PA regulations effectively (2011 MEA/METT, July 2014).
	13	Apathetic and Inactive LGU	Conflicts of interest among local executives and frequent changes in leadership hinder enforcement of environmental laws (2011 MEA/METT and consultative workshop, 2014).
	14	Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation	Lack of community involvement in the previous management plan led to a sense of detachment and hindered its implementation (2011 MEA/METT, July 2014).
	15	Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning	Private sector representation in PAMB meetings and membership is lacking, affecting conservation efforts (KII and consultation workshop, July 2014).
	16	Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB	DENR lacks sufficient manpower and funding to effectively protect AMWS, impacting enforcement efforts (2008 and 2011 MECA/METT findings).
	17	Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management	Insufficient funding for PAMB operations hinders the implementation of management plans and activities (2008 and 2011 MECA/METT findings).

Note: Adopted from the AMWS PAMP 2014-2019 identified threats.

The formula below represents the matrix for the pairwise calculation of the top stressors:

Equation 1 Pairwise comparison matrix equation

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{w_1}{w_2} & \dots & \frac{w_1}{w_n} \\ \frac{w_2}{w_1} & 1 & \dots & \frac{w_2}{w_n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{w_n}{w_1} & \frac{w_n}{w_2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \frac{1}{a_{12}} & 1 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{1}{a_{1n}} & \frac{1}{a_{2n}} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The square matrix (A) used for pairwise comparisons has an equal number of rows and columns. The criterion weights can be computed using λ_{max} , the largest value in this matrix, as follows:

Equation 2 Criterion weights equation

$$AW = \lambda_{max}W$$

To test whether inconsistency is tolerable within the judgment results, compute the CI, which stands for Consistency Index. Whenever CI exceeds acceptable levels, it shows that inconsistent levels are high. This is calculated using Saaty's recommended formula.

Equation 3 Consistency index equation

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$$

When matrix A is consistent, that means all other values below its diagonal sum up to zero, making the Consistency Index (CI) equal to 0. CI was computed by Saaty for several matrices of similar dimensions. To make a standardized ratio measure for

comparison between different matrices of varying sizes, Saaty introduced a consistency ratio, a scaled version of the CI. Following this definition:

Validation of Consistency

Equation 4 Consistency ratio equation

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RC_y}$$

The criterion for validity determination was set by Saaty (2004) at 0.10 and can be used in evaluating any judgment or decision made by an individual. If the Consistency Ratio (CR) surpasses this threshold, it casts doubt on the trustworthiness of the judgments. In such situations, the informants should review and alter his/her judgments until they achieve a CR value below 0.10, as advised by Saaty. Furthermore, Saaty suggested some thresholds for size three and four matrices, proposing that 0.5 and 0.8 are appropriate thresholds for these cases, respectively.

IX. RESULTS

The study on soil moisture analysis in the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) reveals significant changes from 2018 to 2023, with Marbon and Caimpugan Peatlands experiencing varying moisture levels. Increased moisture correlates with higher rainfall intensity, particularly in the western portion of the marsh, and a slight temperature decrease. These findings highlight the dynamic interplay between soil moisture, rainfall, and temperature, which is crucial for understanding peatland resilience. Moreover, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) underscores soil moisture as a top parameter indicator for resilience, alongside other stressors like temperature anomalies and socio-economic challenges. Validation through consistency ratios strengthens the reliability of the research findings, providing valuable insights for AMWS management.

Soil Moisture Analysis Using Remote Sensing Result

There is an increase in moderately (dark blue) and slightly wet (light blue) areas within the boundary of Marbon Peatland from 2018 to 2023. For Caimpugan Peatland, there is also an increase of slightly dry (yellow) and a decrease of moderately dry (orange) areas within its boundary (Figure 4).

This increase in soil moisture from 2018 correlates with the increase in rainfall rate intensity at the western portion of the marsh, from a maximum rainfall rate of 8.9mm/year for 2015-2018 to 10.9mm/year for 2019-2022 (Figure 5). There is a positive correlation between soil moisture and rainfall rate in AMWS.

Figure 4. Soil moisture analysis result maps from 2018 and 2023.

Figure 5. The left-hand map shows the average rainfall rate from 2015 to 2018, and the right-hand map shows the average rainfall rate from 2019 to 2022.

Additionally, this positive correlation is supported by temperature conditions in the marsh (Figure 6). The remotely sensed temperature data for AMWS indicates that the maximum temperature from 2015 to 2018 was 27.13°C, while the maximum temperature from 2019 to 2022 was 26.93°C, lower than the previous years. If AMWS is moister and the rainfall rate is higher, it generally indicates lower temperatures. This is because moist conditions and high rainfall typically lead to cooling effects on the environment. High levels of moisture in the atmosphere can inhibit temperature rise by absorbing heat energy through evaporation and transpiration, which can keep temperatures relatively lower compared to drier conditions.

Figure 6. Annual average temperature condition in AMWS from 2015 to 2018, and from 2019 to 2022.

Overall, there is a positive correlation between high soil moisture, high rainfall rate, and lower temperature changes in AMWS from 2015 to 2023, coinciding with the boundary expansion in 2018.

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) Result

According to the AHP pair-wise questionnaire from the 10 key informants, the top indicator for peatland resilience is soil moisture, which garnered 16% among the 18 identified parameters, as reflected in Table 3. The next top parameters are temperature anomaly from climate change indicator (15%), illegal cutting of trees (environmental) (11%), inadequate DENR personnel to support PA management (socio-economic) (11%), and conversion of land to agriculture (socio-economic) (11%).

Table 3

Ranking of Parameters Based on AHP Pair-wise Consolidated Responses of Key Informants

Ranking of Parameters	Weights of Criteria	% Weights of Criteria	Rank
Soil Moisture	0.161	16.05%	1st
Temperature Anomalies	0.152	15.20%	2nd
Illegal cutting of Trees	0.111	11.12%	3rd
Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management	0.110	11.01%	3rd
Conversion of land to agriculture	0.110	11.01%	3rd
Change in Rainfall Rate	0.080	8.01%	4th
Small-scale mining upland	0.072	7.20%	5th
Sedimentation nutrient loading	0.041	4.12%	6th
Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning	0.030	3.00%	7th
Eutrophication	0.029	2.87%	8th
Poor-solid waste management	0.018	1.80%	9th
Illegal settlement	0.018	1.80%	9th
Lack of IP representation in PAMB	0.018	1.80%	9th
Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation	0.010	1.00%	9th
Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB	0.012	1.20%	10th
Unsustainable livelihood	0.010	1.01%	10th
Apathetic and Inactive LGU	0.010	1.00%	10th
Weak Tourism	0.008	0.80%	11th
Total	1.000	100.00%	

The number of stressors arising from the socio-economic aspect comprises 56% of the total threats prevailing in AMWS. However, the overall weight of these stressors is only 34%, as depicted in Figure 7. There are only two identified stressors from climate change; however, they account for 23% of the overall stressors. Similarly, there are five identified stressors for environmental aspects, but their weight is close to that of climate change, at 27%.

Figure 7. Number and percent weight of the identified stressors.

Legend:		Number of Stressors	Weight of Stressors
	Soil Moisture	1	16%
	Climate Change	2	23%
	Environmental	5	27%
	Socio-economic	10	34%
Total		18	100%

Validation Method: Consistency Ratio

Among the ten key informants listed in Table 4, seven passed the consistency ratio of <0.10 , while three were inconsistent with their responses. The average consistency ratio for the ten informants is 0.098, which is considered highly consistent regarding the questionnaire and their responses.

Table 4*Key Informants' Information with Confidential Names and Their Consistency Ratio*

No.	Letter	Position	Office/Company	Consistency Ratio
1	A	Forester	DENR-CENRO, Tubod, Surigao Del Norte	0.092
2	B	Forester	DENR-CENRO, Bayugan City, Agusan del Sur	0.070
3	C	Geologist	Philsaga Mining Corporation, Agusan del Sur	0.091
4	D	Chemical Engineer	Philsaga Mining Corporation, Agusan del Sur	0.082
5	E	Geologist	National Irrigation Administration	0.108
6	F	Geologist	Environmental Management Bureau	0.093
7	G	Executive Secretary	LGU-Municipality of Bunawan	0.145
8	H	Former Brgy. Captain	LGU-Municipality of Bunawan, Brgy. San Teodoro	0.165
9	I	Instructor/Geologist	Academe, Caraga State University, Agusan del Norte	0.052
10	J	Instructor/Geologist	Academe, University of Southeastern Philippines, Davao City	0.080
Total Consistency Ratio				0.098

X. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil moisture analysis conducted in the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) between 2018 and 2023 provides crucial insights into the dynamic changes within the ecosystem, particularly in the Marbon, Talacogon and the Caimpugan Peatlands. The observed increase in moderately and slightly wet areas in Marbon Peatland is also observed in the slight increase in slightly dry areas in Caimpugan Peatland. These changes are notably influenced by variations in rainfall intensity, with the western portion of the marsh experiencing higher rainfall rates. The correlation between increased soil moisture and higher rainfall intensity underscores the significant role of precipitation in shaping soil moisture dynamics within the sanctuary.

Furthermore, the relationship between soil moisture and temperature further elucidates the environmental dynamics in AMWS. The observed decrease in maximum temperatures from 2015 to 2018 (27.13°C) to 2019 to 2022 (26.93°C) correlates with higher soil moisture levels and increased rainfall rates. This inverse relationship between moisture and temperature reflects the cooling effects of moist conditions and higher precipitation. The absorption of heat energy through processes like evaporation and transpiration mitigates temperature rise, highlighting the complex interplay between soil moisture, rainfall, and temperature in regulating environmental conditions within AMWS.

Moreover, applying the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) emphasizes the significance of soil moisture as a critical parameter indicator for peatland resilience, as identified by key informants. The AHP results highlight the multifaceted nature of stressors impacting AMWS, with soil moisture, temperature anomalies, illegal tree-cutting, and socio-economic challenges emerging as primary concerns. These findings

underscore the importance of considering multiple factors in assessing ecosystem resilience and prioritizing conservation efforts.

Overall, integrating soil moisture analysis, rainfall intensity, temperature data, and AHP results provides a comprehensive understanding of the environmental dynamics and stressors affecting AMWS. These findings offer valuable insights for informed decision-making and management strategies to preserve the sanctuary's ecological integrity amidst ongoing environmental changes and anthropogenic pressures.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of soil moisture dynamics, rainfall intensity, temperature changes, and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) results in the Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS), several strategic recommendations can be made to enhance ecosystem resilience and inform management practices. Firstly, given the significant correlation between soil moisture and rainfall intensity, monitoring and managing water resources effectively is imperative, particularly in areas experiencing higher precipitation. This may involve implementing measures to regulate water flow, prevent flooding, and promote sustainable land use practices to mitigate erosion and soil degradation. Specific examples are the installation of hydrological monitoring stations, construction of check dam and retentions basins, implementation of sustainable drainage systems, establish vegetative buffer zones along waterways to establish soil stability, adoption of tillage-free practice, terracing and contour plowing, engaging local communities in water management practices, and conducting regular maintenance and inspection of existing water management infrastructure, and to ensure that hydrological monitoring basins are functioning correctly.

Secondly, recognizing the inverse relationship between soil moisture status and temperature changes, efforts should be made to safeguard against potential temperature extremes that could adversely impact ecosystem health. This could include strategies such as reforestation and vegetation restoration to provide natural cooling mechanisms and reduce anthropogenic heat sources within the sanctuary.

Thirdly, in light of the AHP findings highlighting soil moisture as a critical parameter indicator for peatland resilience, conservation initiatives should prioritize maintaining optimal soil moisture levels to support ecosystem functions and biodiversity. This may

involve implementing wetland restoration projects (Zedler & Kercher, 2005), enhancing water retention capacities (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2007), and minimizing activities that disrupt natural hydrological processes (Joosten et al., 2012).

Additionally, addressing identified stressors such as illegal tree cutting or timber encroachment, unsustainable land use practices, and socio-economic challenges is crucial for promoting long-term sustainability in AMWS. Collaborative efforts involving government agencies, local communities, and stakeholders should be prioritized to address these threats and ensure effective protection and management of the sanctuary.

In conclusion, integrating soil moisture analysis, rainfall intensity, temperature data, and AHP results provides valuable insights for developing strategic management plans to preserve AMWS' ecological integrity. By implementing targeted interventions to address key stressors and promote ecosystem resilience, AMWS can continue to serve as a vital habitat for biodiversity while supporting sustainable livelihoods for local communities.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

AHP Questionnaire

Assessment of Agusan Marsh Wildlife Sanctuary (AMWS) Peatland's Resilience to Climate Change, Socio-Economic, and Environmental Stressors by Estimating Soil Surface Moisture Using Remote Sensing

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Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) Questionnaire

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a system that combines math and psychology to organize and analyze complicated choices. Thomas L. Saaty created it in 1970s, and since then, it has been modified. It consists of three parts: the primary objective or problem you're attempting to resolve, all potential solutions, or alternatives, and the standards by which you'll evaluate the option. By putting the decision's criteria and potential outcomes into numerical form and connecting them to the main objective, AHP offers a logical framework for making necessary decisions.

This survey seeks expert opinions on the corresponding importance of various criteria, sub criteria, and parameters that should be considered when selecting gold and copper potential using AHP.

No.	Indicators Parameters for Peatland Resilience
1	Soil Moisture (Main)
2	Change in Rainfall Rate (Climate Change)
3	Temperature Anomalies (Climate Change)
4	Illegal cutting of Trees (Environmental)
5	Small-scale mining upland (Environmental)
6	Sedimentation nutrient loading (Environmental)
7	Poor solid waste management (Environmental)
8	Eutrophication (Environmental)
9	Illegal settlement (Socio-Economic)
10	Unsustainable livelihood (Socio-Economic)
11	Conversion of land to agriculture (Socio-Economic)
12	Weak tourism (Socio-Economic)
13	Lack of IP representation in PAMB (Socio-Economic)
14	Apathetic and Inactive LGU (Socio-Economic)
15	Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation (Socio-Economic)
16	Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning (Socio-Economic)
17	Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB (Socio-Economic)
18	Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management (Socio-Economic)

Appendices 1 AHP Questionnaire

INTENSITY OF IMPORTANCE	DESCRIPTION	EXPLANATION
1	Equal Importance	The two indicators have equal contribution to the vulnerability component
3	Moderate Importance	Importance contribution of Indicator A is slightly favored over Indicator B
5	Strong Importance	Contribution of Indicator A is strongly favored over Indicator B
7	Very Strong Importance	Contribution of Indicator A is strongly favored over Indicator B
9	Extreme Importance	Indicator A has the highest possible contribution over Indicator B
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate Values	When compromise is needed
Reciprocals: 1/2, 1/4, 1/3, etc.	These intensities can be used for elements that are very close in importance	

Top Stressors Parameter for Peatland Resilience																		
Indicator A	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1/2	1/3	1/4	1/5	1/6	1/7	1/8	1/9	Indicator B
Soil Moisture (Main)																		Change in Rainfall Rate (Climate Temperature Anomalies (Climate Change))
																		Illegal cutting of Trees (Environmental)
																		Small-scale mining upland (Environmental)
																		Sedimentation nutrient loading (Environmental)
																		Poor solid waste management (Environmental)
																		Eutrophication (Environmental)
																		Illegal settlement (Socio-Economic)
																		Unsustainable livelihood (Socio-Economic)
																		Conversion of land to agriculture (Socio-Economic)
																		Weak tourism (Socio-Economic)
																		Lack of IP representation in PAMB (Socio-Economic)
																		Apathetic and Inactive LGU (Socio-Economic)
																		Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation (Socio-Economic)
																		Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning (Socio-Economic)
																		Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB (Socio-Economic)
																	Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management (Socio-Economic)	

Down to

Top Stressors Parameter for Peatland Resilience																		
Indicator A	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1/2	1/3	1/4	1/5	1/6	1/7	1/8	1/9	Indicator B
Apathetic and Inactive LGU (Socio-Economic)																		Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation (Socio-Economic)
																		Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning (Socio-Economic)
																		Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB (Socio-Economic)
																		Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management (Socio-Economic)

Top Stressors Parameter for Peatland Resilience																		
Indicator A	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1/2	1/3	1/4	1/5	1/6	1/7	1/8	1/9	Indicator B
Non-involvement of on-site communities in project implementation (Socio-Economic)																		Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning (Socio-Economic)
																		Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB (Socio-Economic)
																		Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management (Socio-Economic)

Top Stressors Parameter for Peatland Resilience																		
Indicator A	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1/2	1/3	1/4	1/5	1/6	1/7	1/8	1/9	Indicator B
Top-Down and Prescriptive Management Planning (Socio-Economic)																		Non representation of the private sector and tourism authority in the PAMB (Socio-Economic)
																		Lacking of DENR personnel to support PA management (Socio-Economic)